

Scientific Analysis of the Concepts of Rally, Assembly and Demonstration

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Abstract: This article discusses the right of citizens to organize assemblies and their legal basis, various forms and political and social role, and discusses the fact that rallies, meetings and demonstrations allow citizens to freely express their opinions and put forward demands and proposals on current issues in society. Analyzing the legal basis and international experience, the importance of exercising this right in forming a democratic and pluralistic society is studied. In particular, The article provides a detailed understanding of how rallies, meetings and demonstrations are regulated in the country's legislation and their purpose and forms from the point of view of international law, and the opinions of scholars are scientifically analyzed. The article also focuses on the purpose, nature and social significance of these events, and examines the problems and gaps in national legislation regarding them.

Keys words: Rally, assembly, demonstration, right to assemble, human rights, protests.

The right to assemble is today considered one of the fundamental and inalienable political rights of citizens.

Citizens freely express their opinions by organizing assemblies. They can also put forward demands and proposals on various issues of the country's economic, political, and socio-cultural life. In turn, a number of questions naturally arise about how the freedom of assembly is interpreted in scientific and legal literature, as well as what forms it exists. As we systematically analyze the studied data, we will dwell on each concept separately.

“**Assembly** is one of the fundamental human rights, characterized by the participation of individuals or groups of individuals, associations and organizations. In this context, assemblies serve a number of purposes, including expressing the opinion or discontent of a minority, preserving and developing culture. Assemblies are a means of expressing the common interests of a group of people. In exercising the right to assemble, the freedom to join associations, communicate, move, cross state borders, and freedom of speech, thought, and conscience are complementary. Assemblies are considered an important factor in the development of the individual and are of great importance in the development of society¹. ”

Rallies, meetings and demonstrations are complementary concepts that are held to solve the political, social or economic problems of citizens. In this, the religion, traditions, political consciousness of the nation, the stage of development of the state play an important role. In the East and other Muslim

¹ Pukovodyashchie principle po svobode mirnyx sobraniy . Izdanie 2-e / Opublikovano BDIPCh OBSE, 2011 . - S. 15. [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/d/6/83237.pdf> (accessed 15.01.2022)

countries, holding rallies and other demonstrations is considered to be events that are completely contrary to the worldviews that are consistent with national and religious values ².

The coverage of rallies through the media ensures that people's opinions and appeals are disseminated to a wide audience. Therefore, the positive changes in the life of society also depend on the communicative potential of rallies.

Holding meetings based on democratic principles serves to build a pluralistic and tolerant society.

In addition, a number of definitions are given for holding meetings. For example, the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language states that it is a gathering of people to exchange ideas or resolve an issue; the Wikipedia encyclopedia states that it is ³a type of right related to "first generation" human rights ⁴(*civil and political*), which includes holding rallies, pickets, demonstrations, and meetings.

The "Guidelines on Peaceful Assembly" developed by the OSCE Office for Democratic Institutions and Human Rights defines "assembly" as a gathering of a group of individuals in a public place for a specified period of time to express a common interest.

According to it, it is stated that at least two people must participate in gatherings (except for pickets), and they are divided into two types depending on the type of gathering, namely:

- 1) held in a fixed location – meeting, flash mob, rally, demonstration, picket;
- 2) It is emphasized that the gatherings can be divided into types such as street marches, which are held with the participants moving ⁵.

Gatherings, in particular, rallies, meetings, demonstrations, street marches, etc., in turn, are considered a type of mass event, and I. Ismailov, MZ Ziyodullayev, SN Gordeyev and AP Korenev divided mass events into socio-political, cultural-popular, sports-entertainment and religious types, depending on the purpose of organizing them, their nature, the number of participants, the place of their holding, and the degree of threat to public safety ⁶.

ST Akhmedova, on the other hand, emphasized demonstrations, rallies, street marches and other similar events as a type of socio-political event, characterized these events by the need for high-level organizational, financial, technical and information dissemination (advertising) support, as well as the specificity of the composition of the event participants ⁷, and also defined the concept of "mass event" by including meetings, rallies, demonstrations, pickets, and street marches ⁸.

²Constitutional law of foreign countries: textbook / Editor-in-chief: prof. AAzizkhoyjayev: – T.: TDYI publishing house, 2010.– P. 590. [Electronic resource] // URL: [https://n.ziyouz.com/books/kollej_va_otm_darslikari/huquq/Xorijiy%20mamlakatlar%20konstitutsiyaviy%20huquqi%20\(A.Azizkhoyjayev%20va%20b.\).pdf](https://n.ziyouz.com/books/kollej_va_otm_darslikari/huquq/Xorijiy%20mamlakatlar%20konstitutsiyaviy%20huquqi%20(A.Azizkhoyjayev%20va%20b.).pdf) (accessed 15.01.2022)

³Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language / edited by A. Madvaliyev. T, 2006-2008. – P. 272. [Electronic resource] // URL: https://n.ziyouz.com/books/uzbek_tilining_izohli_lugati/O'zbek%20tilining%20izohli%20lug'ati%20-%20Y.pdf (accessed 15.01.2022)

⁴Freedom of assemblies [Electronic resource] // URL: https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Freedom_of_Assemblies (accessed 15.01.2022)

⁵Pukovodyashchie principle po svobode mirnyx sobraniy . Izdanie 2-e / Opublikovano BDIPCh OBSE, 2011 . - S. 33-34.

⁶Ismailov I., Ziyodullaev M.Z., Gordeev S.N. Administrativnaya deyatelnost organov vnutrennix del: uchebnik. - T., 2014. - S. 342; Administrativnaya deyatelnost organov vnutrennix del. Chast Osobennaya: ucheb. / pod ed. A.P. Koreneva. - M., 1999. - S. 286.

⁷Akhmedova S.T. Mass ownership is a factor riska voznikoveniya massovykh besporyadkov // Zakonnost i pravoporyadok v sovremennom obshchestve. – 2016. – no. 29. - S. 71.

⁸Akhmedova S. The essence of maintaining public order and ensuring the safety of citizens. // ANALYSIS OF THE LEGISLATION OF UZBEKISTAN - UZBEK LAW REVIEW - OBZOR ZAKONODATELSTVA UZBEKISTAN. No. 2, 2016. – P. 42-46.

In his works, AA Khudoyberdiev noted demonstrations, rallies, marches, and gatherings as socio-political types of mass events, and divided these events into types based on their nature (international, national, regional, local) and legality (permitted and unauthorized) ⁹.

However, Resolution No. 205 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of 2014 stipulates that conferences, congresses, congresses and other events are socio-political types of mass events, and does not mention that rallies, meetings, demonstrations, street marches are socio-political mass events. It is also established that this Government Resolution, which approved the “Rules for Holding Mass Events”, does not apply to rallies, meetings, street marches and demonstrations ¹⁰. From this it can be concluded that in national legislation, meetings, meetings, street marches and demonstrations are not considered as mass events, and national legislation refutes the opinion of I. Ismailov, MZ Ziyodullayev, SN Gordeyev, ST Akhmedova, AA Khudoyberdiev, AP Korenev and other scholars.

In particular, in the works of TA Karpenko, meetings, rallies, demonstrations, street marches, pickets, elections, congresses of political parties, and congresses are noted as socio-political types of mass events ¹¹.

In our opinion, based on the conclusions developed based on the results of the analysis of the work carried out by ST Akhmedova and others, although Resolution No. 205 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of 2014 does not regulate the holding of rallies, meetings, demonstrations, street marches, as well as other similar events, when explaining the concept of "mass event", it is necessary to note these events as a socio-political type of mass events.

Based on the above, we consider it appropriate to define the concept of "right to assemble", and the definition given to this concept should be as follows, namely, *the right to assemble is the right of citizens to peacefully carry out their social activities, guaranteed by the country's constitution*.

Below, we will discuss the types of gatherings that are recorded as public events.

A rally is a public gathering dedicated to an important event, often to discuss political issues ¹².

From the above definition, it can be seen that rallies are gatherings held by the public to protest some important political event.

In accordance with this idea, according to Russian scientists N.Yu. Shvedova and our national scientists M.X. Rustambayev, it is emphasized that “a rally is a gathering of a group of people gathered to discuss political issues ¹³.” However, this definition given by scientists is of general importance and cannot sufficiently reveal the essence of the concept of “rally.” For this reason, other scientists have given different definitions to this concept.

Russian scholars AB Barikhin, SI Ozhegov, and DN Ushakov defined a rally as a mass gathering of citizens to discuss social and other issues, in addition to political issues, and emphasized that it can be of

⁹Khudoyberdiev A. Teoreticheskie osnovy obespecheniya okhrany obshchestvennogo ryadka i obespecheniya bezopasnosti pri provedenii massovykh meropriyatiy //SCIENCE AND WORLD. - 2013. - S. 58.

¹⁰ That source

¹¹ Karpenko Tatyana Andreevna. Administrativnaya otvetstvennost za narushenie obshchestvennogo ryadka i obshchestvennoy bezopasnosti pri provedenii massovykh meropriyatiy: dissertation ... candidate of legal studies: 12.00.14 / Karpenko Tatyana Andreevna; [Mesto zashchity: Dalnevostochnyy yuridichesky institut MVD Rossii].- Khabarovsk, 2015.- 197 p.

¹²Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language / edited by A. Madvaliyev. T, 2006-2008. – P. 602. [Electronic resource] // URL: https://n.ziyouz.com/books/uzbek_tilining_izohli_lugati/O'zbek%20tilining%20izohli%20lug'ati%20-%20M.pdf (accessed 15.01.2022)

¹³ Tolkovyy slovar russkogo zhyzika s vklyucheniem swedeniy o proishkhojdenii slov / RAN. Institute of Russian Language. V.V. Vinogradova, Otv. ed. N.Yu. Shvedova. – M., 2011: Publishing Center "Azbukovnik". – P. 451.; Studying the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan: A textbook for non-legal areas of the bachelor's degree. – T.: "Uzbekistan" 2001. – P. 186.; Constitutional law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Editor-in-chief: Doctor of Law, prof. A.Kh. Saidov. – T.: Publishing House of the TYUI, 2005. – P. 228.

a demand, benevolent (support) or protest nature¹⁴. Although the definition reveals a number of aspects of this concept, it cannot be fully agreed with, since it does not take into account that a rally can be held in response to the actions of an official or organization.

On the contrary, according to other Russian scholars such as Yu.I. Fedinsky, A.Ya. Sukharyova, VE Krutskikh, "a rally is a reaction of citizens to the actions of an official or organization on important socio-political issues¹⁵," we can see that the definition they gave did not take into account the opinions of the above scholars and we can partially agree with this definition.

In addition, according to the Uzbek scholar U.Sh. Husainov, regarding the rally and the process of holding it: "a rally is a type of meeting held in the open air, and usually, in such public speeches, the organizers and participants send a resolution to the government, which expresses some demand, to officials or citizens¹⁶."

Speaking directly about the concept of "rally", the Legal Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan states that "rally is an English expression, and in Uzbek it is a meeting held to resolve some important event, political, socio-economic issues. When we say rally, we usually mean a gathering of a certain political group, mass movement, or production organization or association, usually in a festive mood or dissatisfied with state authorities, in city centers to express their opinions and demands¹⁷."

In addition, according to the legislation of the Republics of Kazakhstan and Belarus, a rally is defined as "a mass gathering of citizens at a specified time and place using sound-amplifying technical devices, posters, banners and other means to express their opinions on socially important issues or on the actions or inaction of officials and organizations¹⁸."

The legislation of the Republic of Turkmenistan defines a "rally as a mass action aimed at drawing the attention of state bodies to existing socio-political problems, in which citizens freely express their opinions at a predetermined place and time."¹⁹, - it was emphasized.

Also, on January 9, 2022, about 150 citizens in Bishkek protested against the arrest of a jazz performer from the Kyrgyz Republic during protests in Kazakhstan²⁰, on January 16, 2022, a rally dedicated to the support of the people of Mali for the Russian Federation and strengthening cooperation between states²¹, on March 2, 2019, in Miass, against the pollution of Lake Turgoyak, a tourist destination located on the territory of the Russian Federation²², on November 5, 2021, in Glasgow,

¹⁴A.B. Come on. Bolshaya yu ridicheskaya e encyclopedia. (Series "Professionalnye spravochniki i entsiklopedii") - M.: Kniznyy mir, 2010. - S. 456 . Ojegov S.I. Tolkovyy slovar russkogo zhyzka: Ok. 100,000 words, terms and phrases / S.I. Ojegov; Pod ed. Prof. L.I. Skvortsova. - 26-e izd., ispr. i dop. - M.: OOO "Izdatelstvo Onyx"; OOO "Izdatelstvo "Mir i Obrazovanie", 2010. - S. 296 . Ushakov D.N. Tolkovyy slovar sovremennogo russkogo zhyzka, D.N. Ushakov - M.: "Adelant", 2013. - S. 303.

¹⁵ Big explanatory dictionary of official terms: Bolee 8000 terms / Sost. Yu.I. Fedinsky. - M.: OOO "Izdatelstvo Astrel": OOO "Izdatelstvo AST", OOO "Transitkniga", 2004. - S. 454 . Bolshoi yuridi chesky slovar / Pod ed. A. Ya. Sukhareva, V.E. Krutskikh. - M.: INFRA-M. 2000. – B. 335.

¹⁶Constitutional law of foreign countries: textbook / Editor-in-chief: prof. AAAzikhodjayev: - T.: TDYI publishing house, 2010. – P. 139.

¹⁷Legal Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan / Responsible for the publication R.A. Mukhitdinov and others; responsible editor N. Toychiev. – T.: Adolat, 2009. – P. 310.

¹⁸Republic of Kazakhstan Kazakhstan № 333-VI ZRK " Organization and implementation of Mirnyx Sobrani in the Republic of Kazakhstan " dated May 25, 2020 . Article 1.; Law of the Republic of Belarus No. 114-Z "O massovykh meropriyatiyakh ot December 30, 1997. Article 2.

¹⁹Z akon Republic of Tajikistan No. 1169 "O sobraniyakh, mitingakh, demonstratsiyakh i ulichnykh shestviyakh " on December 31, 2014 . Article No. 1.

²⁰B Bishkeke proshel meeting protiv zaderjaniya kirgizskogo djazmena v Kazakhstan [Electronic source] // URL: <https://ria.ru/20220109/kazakhstan-1767043071.html> (accessed on January 20, 2022)

²¹Jiteli Mali proveli mnogotysyachnyy miting v podderjku Rossii [Electronic source] // URL: <https://ria.ru/20220116/miting-1768038577.html> (accessed on January 20, 2022)

²²V Miasse segodnya sostoitsya miting za sokhranenie chistoty ozero Turgoyak [Electronic source] // URL: https://gubernia74.ru/articles/news/1088992/?utm_source=yxnews&utm_medium=desktop (accessed on January 20, 2022)

Great Britain, against global climate change,²³ and a number of similar rally actions, and analyzing the above definitions, in our opinion, the definition of a rally should be as follows, that is, a rally is a public gathering *on issues of current social importance, using technical means and propaganda materials*, or *The mass participation of citizens in a designated place to express their collective opinion in order to express their goodwill (support) or protest against the actions (inaction) of a person or organization.*

A meeting is a gathering of relevant individuals on a particular issue²⁴.

In accordance with the above general definition, as recognized by Russian scholars AB Barykhin, AB Borisov, SI Ozhegov, N.Yu. Shvedova, DN Ushakov, and the definition in the "Principles on Peaceful Assembly" manual developed by the OSCE Bureau for Democratic Institutions and Human Rights²⁵ as "assembly – a gathering of citizens in a certain place on some issue" does not fully reveal the essence of the concept of "assembly".

According to the Uzbek scholar M. K. Rustambayev, "a meeting is a gathering of certain people, held in a closed building or room. The meeting format can be chosen by the organizers of the meeting to limit the number of participants, but this does not determine the main essence of the meeting²⁶." However, unlike M. K. Rustambayev, Russian scholars A. Ya. Sukhareva and V. E. Krutskikh argued that meetings can be held in the open air, in addition to buildings or closed places²⁷.

Although the opinions presented by the above scholars are considered complementary and aspects related to the place of holding meetings are noted, it is not possible to fully agree with them, since the meetings are not intended to attract the attention of local authorities, state bodies and the public, discuss the actions (inaction) of individuals, agencies and organizations, and for other purposes.

In addition, according to the legislation of the Russian Federation, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan and the Republic of Belarus, a meeting²⁸ is defined as "the joint participation of citizens in a specially designated and equipped place for the purpose of discussing socially important issues, as well as the actions or inaction of individuals, agencies and organizations. "

defines a "meeting as a gathering of citizens to discuss a socially important issue in order to attract the attention of the public, territorial authorities, and state bodies."²⁹

²³ Greta Tunberg i eshche tysyachi klimaticheskikh aktivistov ustroili miting v Glazgo [Electronic source] // URL: <https://daily.afisha.ru/news/56423-greta-tunberg-i-eshe-tysyachi-klimaticheskikh-aktivistov-ustroili-miting-v-glazgo/> (access time 20.01.2022)

²⁴ Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language / edited by A. Madvaliyev. T, 2006-2008. – P. 272. [Electronic resource] // URL: https://n.ziyouz.com/books/uzbek_tilining_izohli_lugati/O'zbek%20tilining%20izohli%20lug'ati%20-%20Y.pdf (accessed 20.01.2022)

²⁵ A. B. Barikhin. B olshaya yuridicheskaya encyclopediya. (Series "Professionalnye spravochniki i entsiklopedii") - M.: Kniznyy mir, 2010. - S. 777 . Borisov A.B. B olshoy legal dictionary. - M.: Kniznyy mir, 2010. - S. 686 . Ojegov S.I. Tolkovyy slovar russkogo zhyzka: Ok. 100,000 words, terms and phrases / S.I. Ojegov; Pod ed. Prof. L.I. Skvortsova. - 26-e izd., ispr. i dop. - M.: OOO "Izdatelstvo Onyx"; OOO "Izdatelstvo "Mir i Obrazovanie", 2010. - S. 593 . Tolkovyy slovar russkogo zhyzka s vklyucheniem swedeniy o proishhojdenii slov / RAN. Institute of Russian Language. V.V. Vinogradova, Otv. ed. N. Yu. Shvedova. - M., 2011: Izdatelsky center "Azbukovnik". - S. 909 . Ushakov D.N. Tolkovyy slovar sovremennogo russkogo yazyka, D.N. Ushakov - M.: "Adelant", 2013. - S. 636 . Pukovodyashchie principle po svobode mirnyx sobraniy . Izdanie 2-e / Publikovano BDIPCh OBSE, 2011 . - S. 139.

²⁶ Studying the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan: A textbook for non-legal areas of the bachelor's degree. – T.: "Uzbekiston" 2001. – P. 186.; Constitutional law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Editor-in-chief: Doctor of Laws, Professor A.Kh. Saidov. – T.: Publishing House of the TSU, 2005. – P. 228.

²⁷ Bolshoi yuridi chesky slovar / Pod ed. A. Ya. Sukhareva, V.E. Krutskikh. - M.: INFRA-M. 2000. - S. 565 .

²⁸ Federal Law of the Russian Federation No. 54-FZ " On meetings, rallies, demonstrations, marches and pickets " dated June 19, 2004 (amended on May 17, 2021) . Article 2.; Republic of Kazakhstan Kazakhstan № 333-VI ZRK " Organization and implementation of Mirnyx Sobrani in the Republic of Kazakhstan " on May 25, 2020 . Article 1.; Law of Turkmenistan "Ob organizatsii i provedenii sobraniy, mitingov, demonstratsiy i drugikh massovykh meropriyatiy" dated February 28, 2015 (S izmeneniyami vnesennym Zakonami Turkmenistana dated 09.06.2018 g. No. 38-VI and 14.03.2020 g. No. 234-VI). Article 1; Law of the Republic of Belarus No. 114-Z "O massovykh meropriyatiyakh ot December 30, 1997. Article 2.

²⁹ Law Republic of Kyrgyzskoy R No. 64 " O mirnyx sobraniyax " on May 23, 2012 . Article 3.; Z akon Republic of Tajikistan No. 1169 "O sobraniyakh, mitingakh, demonstratsiyakh i ulichnykh shestviyakh " on December 31, 2014 . Article No. 1.

Also, the All-Belarusian People's Assembly, which, although it does not have any legal status, is held every five years, the decisions taken by its participants are recorded as proposals to the president,³⁰ the meeting dedicated to the 72nd anniversary of the victory in the War of Resistance Against Japanese Aggression in Nanjing, the People's Republic of China,³¹ and a number of similar assembly actions, and having analyzed the above definitions, in our opinion, the concept of an assembly should be defined as follows, namely, *an assembly - a joint participation of citizens in a specially designated and equipped place, without the use of propaganda materials, in order to attract the attention of local authorities, state bodies and the public, to discuss issues of social importance, as well as the actions or inaction of individuals, bodies and organizations.*

A demonstration is a mass movement organized for a specific purpose³².

Russian scholars SI Ojegov, N.Yu. Shvedova and DN Ushakov, “ a demonstration is an open manifestation of socio-political discontent, a public open attitude of demonstrators to one or another issue³³.” However, the definition given by scholars does not fully reveal the meaning of the concept of “demonstration.”

In contrast,³⁴ the opinion that “posters, banners and other propaganda materials may be used during demonstrations” was given by M.K. Rustambayev, U.Sh. Husainov and Y.I. Fedinsky, enriching the definition given by S.I. Ozhegov, N.Yu. Shvedova and D.N. Ushakov.

In addition, the legislation of the Russian Federation and the Republic of Kazakhstan stipulates the possibility of using vehicles during demonstrations³⁵.

The legislation of the Republic of Belarus states that demonstrations can be held on the carriageway of a road (street) for passengers and vehicles, on boulevards, avenues, and squares³⁶.

Also, based on the analysis of the September 2014 demonstration in Hong Kong, China, using umbrellas³⁷, the September 19, 2020 demonstration against quarantine measures on a beach in Tel Aviv, Israel³⁸, the January 26, 2021 "tractor demonstrations" in New Delhi, India, in which citizens participated on horses

³⁰ V Minske startuet Vsebelorusskoe narodnoe sobranie [Electronic resource] // URL : <https://www.rbc.ru/politics/11/02/2021/602298d09a79477d0e7cb001> (accessed on January 20, 2022)

³¹ B Nankine proshlo mejdunarodnoe mirnoe sobranie, posvyashchennoe 72-letiyu pobedy v voyne Soprotivleniya yaponskim zakhvatchikam [Electronic source] // URL : <http://russian.people.com.cn/n3/2017/0816/c31516-9255808.html> (accessed on January 20, 2022)

³² Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language / edited by A. Madvaliyev. T, 2006-2008. – P. 16. [Electronic resource] // URL: https://n.ziyouz.com/books/uzbek_tilining_izohli_lugati/O'zbek%20tilining%20izohli%20lug'ati%20-%20N.pdf (accessed 20.01.2022)

³³ Ojegov S.I. Tolkovyy slovar russkogo zhyzka: Ok. 100,000 words, terms and phrases / S.I. Ojegov; Pod ed. Prof. L.I. Skvortsova. - 26-e izd., ispr. i dop. - M.: OOO "Izdatelstvo Onyx"; OOO "Izdatelstvo "Mir i Obrazovanie", 2010. - S. 140 . Tolkovyy slovar russkogo zhyzka s vklucheniem swedeniy o proishkhojdenii slov / RAN. Institute of Russian Language. V. V. Vinogradova, Otv. ed. N. Yu. Shvedova. - M., 2011: Izdatelsky center "Azbukovnik". - S. 190 . Ushakov D.N. Tolkovyy slovar sovremennogo russkogo zhyzka, D.N. Ushakov - M.: "Adelant", 2013. - S. 112.

³⁴ Rustamboev M.Kh. Commentary on the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. [Revised and supplemented second edition. With amendments and additions as of November 1, 2016] special part / M. Rustamboev. – Tashkent: “Adolat”, 2016. – P. 592.; Constitutional law of foreign countries: textbook / Responsible editor: prof. AAZizkhodzhayev: - T.: TDYI publishing house, 2010. – P. 139.; Large explanatory dictionary of official terms: More than 8000 terms / Compiled by Yu.I. Fedinsky. - M.: OOO “Izdatelstvo Astrel”; OOO “Izdatelstvo AST”, OOO “Tranzitkniga”, 2004. – P. 197.

³⁵ Federal Law of the Russian Federation No. 54-FZ " On meetings, rallies, demonstrations, marches and pickets " dated June 19, 2004 (amended on May 17, 2021) . Article 2.; Republic of Kazakhstan Kazakhstan № 333-VI ZRK " Organization and implementation of Mirnyx Sobrani in the Republic of Kazakhstan " dated May 25, 2020 . Article 1.

³⁶ Law of the Republic of Belarus No. 114-Z "O massovykh meropriyatiyakh ot December 30, 1997. Article 2.

³⁷ "Revolution zontikov": Hong Kong vysupil protiv protivi politiki China [Electronic source] // URL: <https://www.rbc.ru/photoreport/29/09/2014/5429980dcbb20fcee3e9b427> (time of access 20.01.2022)

³⁸ No beach Tel-Aviv proshli demonstratsii protiv povtornogo quarantine [Electronic source] // URL: <http://www.strana.co.il/News/?ID=118083&cat=21> (accessed on January 20, 2022)

in addition to tractors and motorcycles,³⁹ and a number of other similar demonstrations, it is clear that demonstrations, as a rule, can be held in the form of a street march, picket or flash mob, or in other forms. In particular, the "Guidelines for Monitoring Freedom of Peaceful Assembly" developed by the OSCE Office for Democratic Institutions and Human Rights states that demonstrations in the form of funerals expressing political dissent, demonstrations in the form of citizens expressing their protest by moving in convoys of vehicles, including bicycles,⁴⁰ or demonstrations in the form of hunger strikes, building tents and tents in public places as an expression of protest in accordance with the 1995 Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On the Procedure for Organizing and Holding Peaceful Assemblies, Rallies, Street Marches, Pickets and Demonstrations"⁴¹, should be defined as follows: *a demonstration is an organized form of social activity carried out by a group of citizens using propaganda materials to express public sentiment. A demonstration can take the form of a street march, picket, flash mob, or other form.*

A picket is a group of representatives, usually in front of government offices, to express their dissatisfaction with something⁴².

According to Russian scholars DN Ushakov and N.Yu. Shvedova, "a picket is a type of demonstration organized by a group of citizens to express their demands or protests, without the participation of its employees,"⁴³ and this definition does not fully explain the concept of "picket."

At this point, the definition given by Yu.I. Fedinsky: "picketing should be carried out in a fixed place, that is, without moving along a route and without using sound amplification devices" was enriched in⁴⁴ content by U.Sh. Husainov: "a picket is usually a situation where a small group of people (sometimes one person) sits, stands or moves in a circle around some object with posters and banners⁴⁵."

In addition, the legislation of the Russian Federation defines a picket as a form of public expression of opinions by one or more citizens, carried out without the use of technical means of amplification and sound amplification, in front of the object where the picket is held, using posters, banners and other visual propaganda materials, as well as quickly assembled structures⁴⁶.

According to the legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan, a picket is defined as "a citizen of the Republic of Kazakhstan, at a certain time and in a certain place, without movement and without the use of sound amplification equipment, as well as with or without the use of posters, banners and other propaganda materials, expressing public opinion on the actions (inaction) of individuals and (or) bodies, organizations, or on issues of social importance," while in the legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan, a picket⁴⁷ is

³⁹ In New Delhi, 200 people from Zaderzha "traktornoy demonstratsii" [Electronic source] // URL: <https://www.interfax.ru/world/748114> (accessed 20.01.2022)

⁴⁰ Rukovodstvo po monitoringu svobody Mirnyx Sobraniy. Publikovano Buro OSCE po demokraticeskim institutam i pravam cheloveka (BDIPCh), BDIPCh OBSE, 2011. – S. 12.

⁴¹ Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 2126 "Organization of peace, rallies, marches, pickets and demonstrations in the Republic of Kazakhstan" 17 times in 1995. Article 1.

⁴² Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language / edited by A. Madvaliyev. T, 2006-2008. – P. 257 [Electronic resource] // URL: https://n.ziyouz.com/books/uzbek_tilining_izohli_lugati/O'zbek%20tilining%20izohli%20lug'ati%20-%20P.pdf (accessed 20.01.2022)

⁴³ Ushakov D.N. Dictionary of modern Russian language, D.N. Ushakov - M.: "Adelant", 2013. - S. 454. Tolkovyy slovar russkogo zyyka s vlyucheniem swedeniy o proishkhojdenii slov / RAN. Institute of Russian Language. V. V. Vinogradova, Otv. ed. N. Yu. Shvedova. - M., 2011: Izdatelsky center "Azbukovnik". - S. 643.

⁴⁴ Big explanatory dictionary of official terms: Bolee 8000 terms / Sost. Yu.I. Fedinsky. - M.: OOO "Izdatelstvo Astrel": OOO "Izdatelstvo AST", OOO "Transitkniga", 2004. - S. 622.

⁴⁵ Constitutional law of foreign countries: textbook / Editor-in-chief: prof. AAzizkhodzheyev: - T.: TDYI publishing house, 2010. – P. 139.

⁴⁶ Federal Law of the Russian Federation No. 54-FZ " On meetings, rallies, demonstrations, marches and pickets " dated June 19, 2004 (amended on May 17, 2021) . Article 2.; Republic of Kazakhstan Kazakhstan № 333-VI ZRK " Organization and implementation of Mirnyx Sobrani in the Republic of Kazakhstan " dated May 25, 2020 . Article 1.

⁴⁷ Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 2126 "Organization of peace, rallies, marches, pickets and demonstrations in the Republic of Kazakhstan" 17 times in 1995. Article 1.

reflected as a gathering of a small group of individuals in a certain place to express their opinions on issues related to public and state life .⁴⁸

Also, after analyzing the picket actions carried out by Arshak Makichyan on Pushkin Square in Moscow against global climate change⁴⁹, the one held in front of the presidential residence building in Vilnius on September 7, 2019 against the Barnevarn policy⁵⁰, the one held by Ukrainians and Norwegians in front of the Russian Embassy in Oslo, Norway on December 8, 2018 to demand an end to the Russian Federation's aggression against Ukraine⁵¹, the one held in France on February 7, 2022 to draw the government's attention to the problems of refugees⁵², and several other picket actions, as well as the above definitions, we believe that we can give the following definition of picketing, which is enriched in content, namely, *picketing is a form of demonstration that involves the public expression of socially important ideas by one or more citizens using propaganda materials, but without movement and sound amplification.*

In addition, when a picket is held by one person, he has the status of both a participant and an organizer at the same time. In this case, in our opinion, it is appropriate to consider a person who intends to hold a one-person picket as an organizer, taking into account that this person has an interest in holding a picket and that he is the initiator of the picket.

Street march – an organized uprising, a mass movement, against a person or to achieve a goal⁵³.

According to Russian scholars Yu.I. Fedinsky, A.Ya. Sukharyova and V.E. Krutskikh, “street marches are mass movements carried out along the pedestrian and automobile carriageway of the road with the aim of drawing the attention of authorities and the public to some socially important issue⁵⁴.” This definition does not fully cover the content of the concept of “street marches”.

of Uzbek scholar U.Sh. Husainov that “street marches can also be held in the form of marches, and they can also be held throughout settlements, even the entire country or several countries”⁵⁵ expresses the meaning of the concept of “street marches” more broadly, the idea that this event can be held across several countries, based on issues related to state borders, is controversial and it is considered contradictory to agree with this opinion.

According to the legislation of the Republics of Tajikistan and Belarus, "street marches are movements along a predetermined route in order to attract the attention of authorities and the public to a particular problem, and may also aim to express public opinion on socio-political issues⁵⁶."

⁴⁸ Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan " O svobode sobraniy " No. 537-IG dated November 13, 1998. Article 2 .

⁴⁹Arshaka Makichyana's Solo Picket [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://ru.unesco.org/courier/2019-3/odinodnyy-piket-arshaka-makichyana> (accessed 25.01.2022)

⁵⁰ U zdaniya presidentskogo dvortsa v Vilnius – picket protiv politiki Barnevernet [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://www.delfi.lt/ru/news/live/u-zdaniya-prezidentskogo-dvorca-v-vilnyuse-piket-protiv-politiki-barnevernet-82183879> (accessed 10.11.2023)

⁵¹Ukraintsy v Norvegii proveli picket pod posolstvom RF [Electronic resource] // URL: [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://uatv.ua/ukraintsy-v-norvegii-proveli-piket-pod-posolstvom-rf-foto/> (accessed 10.11.2022)

⁵²Zhiteli Frantsii proveli picket, chtoby privlech vnimanie vlastey k probleme bejntsev [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://ont.by/news/zhiteli-frantsii-proveli-piket-htoby-privlech-vnimanie-vlastej-k-probleme-bezhentsev> (accessed 10.11.2022)

⁵³Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language / edited by A. Madvaliyev. T, 2006-2008. – P. 91. [Electronic resource] // URL: https://n.ziyouz.com/books/uzbek_tilining_izohli_lugati/O'zbek%20tilining%20izohli%20lug'ati%20-%20Yu.pdf (accessed 25.01.2022)

⁵⁴ Big explanatory dictionary of official terms: Bolee 8000 terms / Sost. Yu.I. Fedinsky. - M.: OOO "Izdatelstvo Astrel": OOO "Izdatelstvo AST", OOO "Transitkniga", 2004. - S. 923 . Bolshoi yuridi chesky slovar / Pod ed. A. Ya. Sukhareva, V.E. Krutskikh. - M.: INFRA-M. 2000. – S. 683 .

⁵⁵Constitutional law of foreign countries: textbook / Editor-in-chief: prof. AAZizkhodjayev: - T.: TDYI publishing house, 2010. – P. 139.

⁵⁶Z akon Republic of Tajikistan No. 1169 "O sobraniyakh, mitingakh, demonstratsiyakh i ulichnykh shestviyakh " on December 31, 2014 . Article No. 1.; Law of the Republic of Belarus No. 114-Z "O massovykh meropriyatnykh ot December 30, 1997. Article 2.

According to the legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan, "street marches may be held without vehicles and with the use of loudspeakers, banners and other propaganda materials ⁵⁷. "

Analyzing the above definitions, we can add the idea that street marches can focus public attention on socially important issues, express public opinion on problems, and be held in the form of marches, while also dedicating them to some historical process or commemoration, or even being held on a festival scale.

In particular, the "Immortal Regiment" held annually on March 16 ⁵⁸; in memory of the participants of World War II, the "Immortal Regiment" held annually throughout the Russian Federation ⁵⁹, the "Belarus pomnit" held throughout the Republic of Belarus ⁶⁰, the "Nikto ne zabit, nichto ne zabito" held throughout the Republic of Ukraine ⁶¹, as well as the ⁶²"Tyagu-Tyagu Umakko" festival held in Japan in June 2019 with solemn marches on horseback through the cities of Takizawa and Morioka ⁶³, the "Ya lyublyu Dnepr" festival held in Dnipro, Ukraine, on September 8, 2018 with the participation of motorcycles under the slogan "Ya lyublyu Dnepr", and the "Nikto ne zabit" festival held in the city of Dnipro, Ukraine ⁶⁴, on March 19, 2013 Held in Shymkent, Kazakhstan with the participation of cars ⁶⁵, held in New York in March 2021 in support of former US President D. Trump ⁶⁶, held on December 12, 2021 in Arkhangelsk, Russian Federation against the QR coding process of citizens ⁶⁷, held on October 10, 2021 in Brussels, Belgium to save the climate⁶⁸ and a number of other similar street marches and analyzing the above definitions, we can give the following author's definition of a street march, namely, *a street march is a form of demonstration that involves the organized movement of citizens along a pedestrian path or a section of a street (road), avenues and squares in a predetermined direction in order to draw public attention to socially important issues or existing problems, as well as to express their position in support of or against a person, organization or process. Street marches can be carried out in cars, motorcycles, bicycles and other permitted means.*

Flashmob – (English: flash mob) is a pre-planned mass action in which a group of people appears in a public place, performs predetermined actions, and then disperses. The gathering of flashmob participants is carried out using communication tools, mainly Internet social networks ⁶⁹.

Recently, flash mobs have emerged as a type of mass event on socio-political issues. The "Basic Principles for Peaceful Assemblies" manual, developed by the OSCE Office for Democratic Institutions and Human

⁵⁷Republic of Kazakhstan Kazakhstan № 333-VI ZRK " Organization and implementation of Mirnyx Sobrani in the Republic of Kazakhstan " dated May 25, 2020 . Article 1.

⁵⁸V Rige proshlo shestvie legionerov SS [Electronic source] // URL: <https://iz.ru/857142/2019-03-16/v-rige-proshlo-shestvie-legionerov-ss> (accessed on January 25, 2022)

⁵⁹ V Moskve prokhodit shestvie «Bessmertnogo polka» [Electronic source] // URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nH9B40FJCw0> (accessed on 25.01.2022)

⁶⁰ Shestvie "Belarus pomnit". Tysyachi lyudey proshli po avenue Nezavisimosti. K nim prisoedinilsya Alexander Lukashenko [Electronic source] // URL: https://www.tvr.by/news/obshchestvo/shestvie_belarus_pomnit_tysyachi_lyudey_proshli_po_prospektu_nezavisimosti_k_nim_prisoedinilsya_alek/ (time of reference 25.01.2022)

⁶¹ Prazdnichnoe shestvie "Nikto ne zabyt, nichto ne zabyto" nachalos v Kieve [Electronic source] // URL: <https://tass.ru/obshchestvo/6416149> (accessed on 25.01.2022)

⁶²Ulichnoe shestvie folkloru desyati gorodov v Fuzhou [Electronic source] // URL: http://russian.news.cn/2018-02/09/c_136960852_2.htm (accessed on January 25, 2022)

⁶³Konnyy prazdnik Tyagu-Tyagu Umakko [Electronic source] // URL: <https://visitjapan.ru/spot/494> (accessed on 01/25/2022)

⁶⁴ Carnival shestvie "Ya lyublyu Dnieper". Parade bikers and motorcycles. carnival. Ukraine, Dnieper, September 8, 2018 [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://www.istockphoto.com/ru/фото/карнавальное-шествие-я-люблю-днепр-парад-байкеров-на-мотоцикл-карнавал-украина-gm1036683022-277499303> (accessed 01/25/2022)

⁶⁵ Vesennee shestvie na avtomobilyakh ustroila molodej Shymkenta [Electronic source] // URL: <https://otyrar.kz/2013/03/vesennee-shestvie-na-avtomobilyakh-ustroila-molodezh-shymkenta/> (time of application 25.01.2022)

⁶⁶ V SShA proshlo shestvie v podderjku Donalda Trampa [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://www.aa.com.tr/ru/mir/v-ssha-proshlo-shestvie-v-podderjku-donald-trampa/2166605> (accessed on January 25, 2022)

⁶⁷ Shestvie protiv QR-code! Arkhangelsk [Electronic source] // URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aLacfvOCB8c> (accessed 01/25/2022)

⁶⁸March "Za klimat" v Brussels [Electronic source] // URL: <https://ru.euronews.com/2021/10/10/brussels-march-for-climate> (accessed on January 25, 2022)

⁶⁹ Flashmob [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Флешмоб> (accessed 25.01.2022)

Rights, defines a flash mob as “a short-term mass movement in which a group of people gather in one place, perform a series of actions, and disperse quickly, incorporating an element of surprise”⁷⁰.

We can also see that there are a number of types of flash mobs today. For example:

artmob (*a specific advertising campaign with artistic value*);

dance flashmob (*music is suddenly played in the crowd and participants perform a group dance, prepared in advance*);

extreme mob (*extreme actions are performed among the public, in which violations of moral principles, petty hooliganism, and offenses against random passers-by may be committed*);

L-mob (*a type of flashmob that lasts a long time (up to a week) based on a script set by the participants, at a time convenient for them*);

farshing (*a performance in which participants perform in a way that deviates from normal psychological, moral, and social norms, including unusual acts such as men dancing in women's clothing, throwing food, and breaking their own phones*);

fan-mob (*a type of flashmob that creates a mass state of joy*);

mob-house (*carried out by participants acting out a life process rather than a scenario for a set period of time*);

i-mob (*a type of flashmob that takes place on Internet networks*);

politmob or sociomob (*a movement dedicated to social or political issues, a simple, fast and safe way to express public opinion or draw attention to specific problems, such as rallies or demonstrations*)⁷¹.

When analyzing the types of flash mobs, we believe that we can cite such types of flash mobs as dance, political, and sociomob as forms of demonstration. After all, we can see that these types of flash mobs embody the expression of public opinion or the drawing of attention to certain problems, and in most cases are dedicated to social or political issues.

Based on the above, we believe that we can give the following definition of a flash mob, namely, *a flash mob is a form of demonstration, a pre-planned mass action, in which a group of people appear in a public place, perform predetermined actions (scenario), and then disperse, in order to express public opinion, draw attention to socio-political issues or specific problems.*

In addition, studies have shown that in recent years, rallies, meetings, and demonstrations have been transformed, that is, they are moving to an online platform. Quarantine rules such as maintaining social distance, banning mass gatherings in public places, and bans on holding mass events during the Covid-19 pandemic have prompted events that used to be held in a traditional (offline) way, including rallies, meetings, and demonstrations, to be held in the virtual world.

These include the “Immortal Regiment” online street march held in the Russian Federation in 2021 during the pandemic⁷², virtual meetings held by business associations in the Russian Federation⁷³, an online flashmob held by doctors under the slogan “We stay at work for you, you stay at home for us!”⁷⁴, the

⁷⁰ Pukovodyashchie principle po svobode mirnyx sobraniy . Izdanie 2-e / Opublikovano BDIPCh OBSE, 2011 . - S. 156.

⁷¹ R. Jantasov. Fleshmoby - prava na svobodu vyrajeniya mneniya. Техническое задание по итогам треннния "Issledovaniya i monitoring v oblasti prav cheloveka", Almaty, 2018. - S. 10. [Electronic source] // URL: https://www.soros.kz/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/ZHANTASOV_web_.pdf (accessed on January 25, 2022)

⁷² About 5 million participants united online-shestvie "Bessmertnogo Polka" [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://rg.ru/2021/05/09/okolo-piati-mln-uchastnikov-obedinilo-onlajn-shestvie-bessmertnogo-polka.html> (accessed 01/25/2022)

⁷³ Tokmakov M.A. Virtualny e sobrania uchastnikov hozyaystvennyx obshchestv v Rossii. Russian science: actual research and development. Sbornik nauchnyx statey XI Vserossiyskoy nauchno-prakticheskoy conference. Samara, 2021 [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=46369179> (accessed on January 20, 2022)

⁷⁴ Flash mob from doctors during quarantine: We stay at work for you, you stay home for us! [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CTbvgduAqBM> (accessed 25.01.2022)

“#MenUchunQadrli (#Senyu)” flashmob competition on social networks ahead of the 29th anniversary of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan held by the “Yuksalish” nationwide movement ⁷⁵, an online flashmob held by the Exponatuz Art Gallery online community against discrimination against women and for gender equality, ⁷⁶and others.

Given the spontaneous spread of information on social networks, it should be noted that virtual rallies, meetings, and demonstrations can also pose a significant threat to public order and security. After all, we can see how important the role of social networks was in the escalation of the "January events" in Kazakhstan in 2022, as well as in the escalation of rallies and demonstrations into mass unrest and a threat to the national security of the state ⁷⁷.

Based on this, we can divide rallies, meetings, and demonstrations into two types based on the form they are held:

Form 1: traditional, i.e. physical participation of citizens in rallies, meetings, and demonstrations;

Form 2: virtual, where citizens organize and participate in rallies, meetings, and demonstrations remotely using the Internet.

Based on the analysis of the above concepts and the practical examples studied, we believe that it is permissible to call a rally, meeting, demonstration and other types of social activity under the general name "gathering", and therefore, we consider the concept of "gathering" to be defined as follows, that is, *a gathering is a general concept that encompasses the implementation of citizens' social activities in the form of a rally, meeting, demonstration or other form. Gatherings can also be held via the Internet.*

In addition, the concepts of "propaganda materials" and "assembly venue" used in holding rallies, meetings, and demonstrations are not covered, and it would be appropriate to provide definitions for them.

Accordingly, based on the social activities studied, in our opinion, the concept of "promotional materials" can be defined as follows, namely, *promotional materials are posters, leaflets, transparencies, banners, slogans, photos, wall newspapers, and other visual aids that additionally serve to increase the impact and relevance of the gatherings.*

The concept of "assembly venue" is defined as follows: *an assembly venue is a building, structure or area specially designated for rallies, meetings and demonstrations held as a form of social activity and with security measures in place.*

In conclusion, we note that in properly organizing rallies, meetings, and demonstrations, it is important to distinguish them from each other, as well as to know the specifics of each event. Holding these events remains one of the basic political rights of citizens in solving socio-political problems, expressing their position on important issues, and supporting or expressing dissatisfaction with the actions (inaction) of any individual, organization, or state body.

⁷⁵#MenUchunQadrli flashmob competition on social networks [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://yuz.uz/news/menuchunqadrli-ijtimoiy-tarmoqlarda-fleshmob-tanlov-> (accessed 25.01.2022)

⁷⁶ Uzbek girls held a flash mob against sexism and domestic violence [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://uz.fergana.media/news/119886/> (accessed 25.01.2022)

⁷⁷ Peskov will not play a role in society and society in Kazakhstan [Electronic source] // URL: <https://iz.ru/1274940/2022-01-10/peskov-ukazal-na-rol-sotcsetei-v-sobytiiax-v-kazakhstane> (accessed on January 25, 2022)